

The influence of product quality, customer value, and lifestyle on purchase decisions for woven fabrics (Study on: West Muna Weaving House)

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Abstract

Fashion is often used as a tool to reveal one's identity and self-worth. One type of traditional Indonesian fashion is woven cloth typical of West Muna Regency. Sales of West Muna woven fabrics are not as smooth as weaving in other areas of Southeast Sulawesi Province. This study aims to analyze the quality of West Muna weaving products, customer value perceptions, and the suitability of lifestyles to consumer purchasing decisions of West Muna weaving. This study uses a quantitative approach with a purposive sampling technique. 133 respondents spread across 3 different regions have given their assessments of the quality of West Muna weaving products, their perceptions of the values of West Muna weaving, and the suitability of their lifestyle to the value and performance of West Muna weaving. The results showed that product quality, customer value, and lifestyle partially and simultaneously influence purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics. The result show that: (1) Product quality has a positive effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving (2) Customer value influences consumer purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving. (3) Lifestyle influences the purchasing decision of West Muna weaving. (4) Simultaneously, product quality, customer value, and lifestyle influence purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics.

Keywords: Product Quality; Customer Value; Lifestyle; Purchase Decision

1. Introduction

Fashion is often used as a reflection of the determinants of social, economic, and social image. Fashion trends in Indonesia have developed from time to time. This is due to the development of the entertainment world, the internet, and the business world. Some of the traditional Indonesian fashions are kebaya, batik, and weaving. In November 2009, batik was named one of the world heritages by UNESCO, because batik is considered rich in symbols and philosophies of Indonesian people's life. In addition to batik, weaving is also a form of local wisdom that is typical of the region which has a very beautiful and enchanting fabric motif design. Each region has a different form of weaving motif and the history behind the motif.

Product quality is the state of a product which includes its features and characteristics, which are able to meet the needs and desires of consumers. Some characteristics of woven fabric products that can be a measure of the quality of a product are the durability of the fabric, the dyeing technique used, aesthetic value, features, price [1], [2], because of consumer demands that prioritize convenience and personalization [3]

When deciding to buy a product, consumers will look at the quality characteristics of the product they have. [4] argues that product quality influences directly or indirectly through purchase motivation on batik purchasing decisions at the Trusmi Cirebon Batik Showroom. One measure of product quality in fashion type of clothing is its aesthetic value in the form of a beautiful motif design that is able to influence consumer purchasing decisions [5], [6]

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West Muna Regency is one of the regions in Indonesia which also has local wisdom products in the form of woven fabrics from West Muna Regency. The weaving motif of West Muna Regency is a triangular motif called the Botupotobo. The motif has a historical story that long ago the parents of the Muna tribe only used a triangular kris to be used as a tool of war, not using a sword. Since the founding of West Muna Regency in 2014, sales of West Muna woven fabrics have been very low. Based on data compiled from the Trade and Industry Office of West Muna Regency in 2020, the total sales of West Muna woven fabrics with the number of weavers in one sub-district were 30 weavers, in one year only able to penetrate the sales figure of 150 pieces of woven fabric. This figure is quite small because when viewed from the total production and sales of woven fabrics per weaver, they are usually able to sell 3 to 5 fabrics per month, and are not sold regularly every day. In addition, the price of West Muna woven fabrics ranges from 200 – 1,750 thousand rupiah. The figure of 200 thousand when compared to woven fabric products in other areas in Southeast Sulawesi Province, is a number that is quite affordable. However, this is not enough to influence consumer purchasing decisions.

In addition, there are several other things that consumers can consider when assessing the quality of a product. These factors are factors that affect the emotional side of consumers so that it has an impact on the assessment of the quality of the product. Customer value is an assessment of a product based on customer perceptions which can be considered by consumers in deciding purchases [7] [8]. The measurement of customer value is very subjective and personal. Customer value measures how much benefit consumers get compared to the sacrifices they have to make to get a product. In terms of motifs, the better, more beautiful, and more complex the motifs are on the cloth, the more confidence consumer will have and the more expensive the price will be. The more expensive the price, the more consumers will show their 'class' in society.

In addition to customer value, lifestyle is also considered capable of contributing to a consumer's consideration in deciding to purchase a product. A person's lifestyle is seen through their daily activities (activities), the things they are interested in from various aspects of life (interests), and their opinions on various issues around them (opinions) [9]. The condition of the activities of the people of West Muna Regency who use weaving a lot, such as when attending social events, office events, being used as office uniforms, used as souvenirs for regional guests who visit, makes woven fabrics a part of the lifestyle of the people of West Muna Regency. So it is worth investigating the relationship between consumer lifestyles and the performance of West Muna weaving, as well as its development, especially in the field of marketing that is able to support the local community's economy. [10] shows that lifestyle has a positive effect on consumer purchasing decisions in the Chennai market location in India, and [4], also revealed that lifestyle influences the purchasing decision of Cirebon Batik.

However, there are also previous studies that give different results about the relationship between product quality, customer value, and lifestyle on purchasing decisions. [11] also revealed that customer value did not influence the purchasing decisions of female consumers at accessories stores in Riyadh City, Saudi Arabia, and [12] revealed that lifestyle did not influence the decision to purchase carpets at a wholesale store in Borujerd City, Iran. Based on the phenomenon of the object of research and the inconsistency of research results obtained regarding the relationship between the same research variables, it is necessary to conduct research to examine and analyze the relationship between product quality, customer value, and lifestyle on purchasing decisions of West Muna woven fabrics.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Product Quality

Product quality is the ability of the product to meet the needs and desires of consumers through various characteristics and attributes that exist in the product [13]. The quality of West Muna woven products is measured by the performance of their products, in this case the comfort felt by consumers when making physical contact or using the woven fabric, the durability of the woven fabric in the form of how strong the thread is woven and the color of the fabric so that it does not fade easily, the aesthetic value of the woven fabric. in the form of the motif of the fabric design, features of woven products in the form of woven product packaging and various types of products sold, and complementary services in the form of things that can make consumers always have the desire to make repeat purchases, one of which is providing information about West Muna woven fabrics by weavers who master all the specifications of the woven products. Product quality will determine the length of the life cycle of a product on the market. Because consumers will really consider the quality of a product and the number of product innovations made to then decide to buy the product. This study uses four dimensions of product quality measurement adapted from the formulation of measurement dimensions by [1], namely product performance, product durability, product aesthetics, and product features, as well as complementary services.

2.2. Customer Value

Customer value is an assessment based on consumer perceptions that are very subjective about a product. Customer value is generally related to the emotional state of consumers. In this study, emotional value talks about the feelings felt by consumers when wearing the West Muna weaving in the form of a sense of confidence, feeling luxurious, and describing self-value through the West Muna weaving used. In addition, how good is the social image of the West Muna weaving so that it can affect the social value felt by consumers when wearing the West Muna weaving motif. [14] said that consumers can consider the value of a product at several different times, namely when deciding to buy it or when feeling the performance of the product, both while using it and when finished using it. This study measures customer value based on the formula [2] and [15] which consists of measuring the values that can be obtained by consumers when they feel the West Muna woven product (emotional value and social value) and when deciding to buy the woven (functional value, price and conditional value).

2.3. Lifestyle

Lifestyle is the way a person lives his life which is done regularly or repeatedly so as to form a pattern. This pattern of life can be seen through the way a person chooses and carries out his daily activities (activities), various things that become his interests (interests), and his opinions on various issues around him. There are many things that affect a person's lifestyle changes, two of which are culture and the surrounding community. Culture is able to influence the values of life that a person holds as well as a person's perspective on something, starting from here patterns and lifestyles are formed so that they are able to influence a person's purchasing decisions for a product. This research studies the suitability of the lifestyle of West Muna weaving consumers to the performance, value, and functionality of West Muna weaving through their activities, interests, and opinions [9] about various things related to West Muna weaving, Fashion, and their personality.

2.4. Decision Purchasing

Furthermore, product quality, customer value, and lifestyle can collaborate as things that are considered by consumers to decide to buy a product. The aesthetic value of the quality of a product is able to influence the emotional state of consumers, is able to affect consumer moods and consumer confidence, so that the two indicators of the two different variables can jointly influence consumers to make purchasing decisions. Consumer behavior (consumer behavior) determines the occurrence of purchasing decisions (consumer-decision making) of a product. Consumer behavior is a very broad field of study, which explains to consumers why, what, when, and how they buy a product or brand [16]. It is very important to know and understand the consumer buying decision-making process. If marketers are able to understand the process of making consumer purchasing decisions well, then they will be able to sell their goods or services successfully [17]. Furthermore, the performance of West Muna woven products with good yarn quality can support consumer activities so that consumers feel comfortable when wearing West Muna woven fabrics. The researcher chose to use the indicators for measuring the purchasing decision variables formulated by [13], namely: (1) Influence from other people, (2) Unanticipated/unexpected situations, and (3) Habits in buying products.

From the literature review. The conceptual framework of this study is shown below:

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis is as follow:

- H1: Product quality influences purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics
- H2: Customer value influences purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics
- H3: Lifestyle influences purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics
- H4: Product quality, customer value, and lifestyle influence purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics.

3. Methods

This research was conducted in West Muna Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province, precisely at the DEKRANASDA Weaving House, West Muna Regency. By using the multiple linear regression analysis method, the sample size of this study was drawn using the Lameshow formula with a minimum sample size of 96 people with the criteria of respondents being more than 17 years old and having bought West Muna weaving at least 2X purchases, so this study uses a purposive sampling method by determining certain criteria on respondents in the sampling technique. This study uses a questionnaire as a data collection instrument with the available answer choices in the form of a Likert Scale score from 1 to 5 intervals, 1 indicates strongly disagree and 5 indicates strongly agrees, and obtained 133 respondents who gave their assessment of product quality, customer value, and their lifestyle on purchasing decisions of West Muna woven fabrics. This research data was tested using SPSS version 23 software.

4. Results and discussion

This study tested 3 independent variables against 1 dependent variable, namely product quality variables (X1), customer value (X2), and lifestyle (X3) on purchasing decisions (Y). Validity and reliability tests were conducted to test all research questionnaire statement items. The instrument validity test was carried out on 40 respondents before the research was carried out, the results of the validity test were obtained based on the r table value of 0.312 with $\alpha = 0.05$, and all items of the questionnaire instrument obtained an r value count > 0.312 so that the instrument was declared valid. Furthermore, the reliability test with Cronbach's alpha value of at least 0.6 and obtained Cronbach's alpha value for each research variable is > 0.6 so that the instrument is declared reliable.

Table 1 Validity and Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's	Decision	Items	R value count	Decision
X1	0.928	Reliable	X1.1.1 to X1.5.3	>0.312	Valid
X2	0.894	Reliable	X2.1.1 to X2.4.3	>0.312	Valid
X3	0.798	Reliable	X3.1.1 to X3.3.3	>0.312	Valid
Y	0.788	Reliable	Y1.1 to Y3.3	>0.312	Valid

Source: Data processed with SPSS version 23

Furthermore, based on the results of multiple regression analysis, the results are obtained as the table below:

Table 2 Regression Test

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.132	2,220		2,312	0.022
	X1	0.237	0.093	0.357	2.536	0.012
	X2	0.214	0.100	0.299	2.155	0.033
	X3	0.248	0.047	0.304	5.303	0.000

Source: Data processed with SPSS version 23.

Based on the data in the regression analysis table above, the regression equation formula is compiled as follows:

$$Y = 0.357X1 + 0.299X2 + 0.304X3$$

Beta coefficient of 0.357 with a positive direction indicates that the effect of product quality on purchasing decisions is unidirectional which is also supported by a probability value (p-value) of $0.000 < 0.05$, so this result shows that product quality has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for Muna woven fabrics. West. The better the quality

of the West Muna woven product, the more it will affect the level of consumer purchasing decisions for the product (H1 is accepted).

Beta coefficient of 0.299 with a positive direction indicates that the influence of customer value on purchasing decisions is unidirectional which is also supported by a probability value (p-value) of $0.000 < 0.05$, so this result shows that customer value has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics. The better and the more benefits consumers feel about the performance of the West Muna woven product, the more it will affect the level of consumer purchasing decisions for the product (H2 is accepted). The Beta coefficient of 0.304 with a positive direction indicates that the influence of lifestyle on purchasing decisions is unidirectional which is also supported by a probability value (p-value) of $0.008 < 0.05$, so this result shows that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics. That is, the lifestyle pattern adopted by West Muna weaving consumers affects the level of consumer purchasing decisions for the product (H3 is accepted).

Furthermore, the F test was conducted to determine the effect of product quality, customer value, and lifestyle on purchasing decisions simultaneously. The following is the ANOVA table of the F test results obtained.

Table 3 F . Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	870,619	3	290,206	68,647	,000 ^b
	Residual	545,351	129	4,228		
	Total	1415,970	132			

Source: Data processed with SPSS version 23 a. Dependent Variable: Y; b. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1

The table above shows the value of rho sig. of $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that product quality (X1), customer value (X2), and lifestyle (X3) have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics at a significant level of 5%, in other words, the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted.

Figure 2 Description of Research Variables

Table 4 Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.784 ^a	0.615	0.606	2.056

Source: Data processed with SPSS version 23, b. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1

The table above shows the R coefficient value of 0.784 or 78.4% which means that product quality, customer value, and lifestyle have a close relationship simultaneously with consumer purchasing decisions of West Muna woven fabrics. The R square value formed is 0.615 or 61.5% which means that the independent variables of product quality (X1), customer value (X2), and lifestyle (X3) are able to explain consumer purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics with a contribution of 61.5%, and the remaining 38.5% is influenced by other variables outside of this study.

4.1. Product quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchase decision

The results of hypothesis testing show that product quality has an effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving. This shows that the better the quality of the product, the more influencing the level of consumer purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving. Based on the respondents' answers to the variable indicators of product quality, West Muna woven fabric does not feel itchy and hot when worn. The weave has a good yarn density so that the West Muna woven fabric is not easily torn when stretched strongly. This is due to the manufacture of West Muna weaving which uses cotton yarn of good quality and the weaving process is carried out in great detail. In addition, consumers also consider that the color of the West Muna woven fabric does not fade when washed or cleaned and is relatively easy to maintain, The same applies to fabric care in general. However, the variety of motif designs that exist in the western Muna weaving is still very lacking.

The results of this study support the theory [18] that the quality possessed by a product is able to increase productivity and profitability which is marked by an increase in sales, in other words an increase in sales can be obtained through how enthusiastic consumers make purchases of a product. Therefore, it is very important for marketers to pay attention to the quality of their products, in this case, weavers are strongly required to know the market's tastes through the product quality of the weaving works they create. [19], [20], [4] and [21] states that product quality influences purchasing decisions.

4.2. Customer Value has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchase decision

Customer value has a positive effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics. Measurement of emotional value is measured through a history of feelings created towards the use of a product [15]. Weaving Muna Barat is considered able to raise their confidence to appear in front of the public. The choice of the type of fashion can affect a person's mood or emotional side. Fashion is synonymous with aesthetic value. The aesthetic value of a fashion must meet two requirements, namely good design and pleasing the eyes. Consumers also agree that the use of West Muna weaving is only at certain times, so that West Muna weaving can be said to be one type of luxury fashion product because its use is limited at certain times. [22] states that luxury products are often indicated by expensive prices, superior quality [23][24], exclusive or not sold anywhere [25][25], seldom [26], beautiful [27], pleasant and of high value to certain community groups [28]. Therefore, wearing the West Muna weaving is able to make consumers feel part of a certain community. The West Muna woven fabric, which is a fashion product with traditional and aesthetic value, is one of the considerations for consumers to wear it because of the positive social image that the fabric has. West Muna woven fabrics is one of the products of Fashion Nusantara which has the value of local wisdom which is poured into the fabric in the form of motif designs and even the color of the fabric.

The results of this study are supported the theories by [14] that consumers consider the concept of value of a product at different times, such as when deciding to buy the product, or while using it, or even after using the product. When wearing the West Muna weaving, consumers feel high confidence due to the condition of the quality of the woven fabric, feel accepted among certain communities, understand that the price set for West Muna weaving is in the expensive price category but still in accordance with the quality of the fabric. The results of this study are in accordance with several previous studies conducted by [7] which states that customer value or customer perceived value has a significant positive effect on consumer purchasing decisions.

4.3. Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on consumer purchase decision

Lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving, which means that consumer lifestyles for West Muna weaving as measured by activities, interests, and consumer opinions or mindsets also influence their considerations in deciding to buy West Muna weaving. Based on the results of this study, which shows that consumer demographics are dominated by respondents with jobs as office workers (PNS and Private Employees), and the average respondent's response is quite high on the statement that the price of West Muna woven fabrics is quite expensive, and the use of West Muna woven fabrics. Which is still limited to certain occasions, the purchase of West Muna woven fabrics is dominated by reasons of necessity. The need as an office employee who requires the wearing of a typical local woven uniform on certain days makes every community who works as a civil servant or private employee must have woven clothes to support the needs of their daily activities. In addition, the price

set for West Muna woven fabrics, the more beautiful and complicated the existing woven motifs are, the higher the price, thus making consumers consider the price to choose woven fabrics with preferred motifs which of course are driven by the needs of their work. The results of this study are in accordance with the results of research in previous studies conducted by [10], [4] dan [29] that lifestyle is able to influence consumer purchasing decisions.

Simultaneously, product quality, customer value, and lifestyle influence purchasing decisions for West Muna woven fabrics. Product quality, customer value, and lifestyle are three independent variables that are different but able to have a significant influence on consumer behavior in the purchasing decision process of West Muna woven fabrics. One of the evidences can be seen from the results of statistical analysis of the coefficient of determination which states that the three independent variables have a close relationship and are able to influence purchasing decisions with a contribution of 61.5%.

One of the product quality measurement indicators used in this study to measure how well the quality of West Muna woven fabric products in the consumer's view, namely the product aesthetics indicator (aesthetics) is able to influence two measurement indicators in the customer value variable, namely emotional value and social value. The aesthetic value of a fashion product is closely related to something that is eye catching or attracts attention. West Muna weaving with various available patterns and motifs can affect the mood of consumers who act as users of the woven fabric. The emotional side of consumers who are very subjective and privacy really plays an important role in determining their enjoyment of the West Muna woven fabric motif.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion above, it can be concluded that product quality has a positive effect on purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving. The better the quality of the resulting product, the higher the consumer purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving. Therefore, improvements and improvements made to the quality of West Muna woven products will increasingly influence consumer purchasing decisions. Furthermore, customer value influences consumer purchasing decisions for West Muna weaving. This means, consumers decide to buy West Muna weaving not only based on the quality of the products owned by West Muna weaving, but consumers also consider the emotional, social, price, and social benefits. And the conditional use of weaving that they felt during their experience of buying the typical West Muna weaving. Furthermore, lifestyle influences the purchasing decision of West Muna weaving. This shows that the lifestyle that consumers live is one of their considerations and reasons for deciding to buy West Muna weaving. Lifestyle, which is measured by indicators of activity, interest, and opinion, is able to describe activities, fashion interests, and a little about the personality of West Muna weaving consumers.

The implication is that weavers need to increase their insight and knowledge about improving the quality of West Muna weaving, especially the aesthetic part, both in terms of knowledge about the color combination of fabrics (color psychology and color types), placement of distances between motifs in one fabric, wealth types of motifs, and so on. So that West Muna woven products can have added value and are highly competitive and are worthy of sale in domestic and foreign markets. Additional knowledge of weavers can be obtained through the implementation of training or workshops by the local government on the placement of motifs and color combinations.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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